

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: CAROL PERDIGUER****FIRST NAME: LAURA****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access) – Grammarly rate of plagiarism 5%.

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office Professional Plus 2013 on Windows 10 Pro

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-13)
4. What is a Style Guide and Why Would I Need One? (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
5. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2021, 44-55)
6. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 27)

ACADEMIC WRITING AT EUCLID

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401 period one is an introduction to academic writing, specifically at EUCLID. EUCLID ACA-401 Period 1 Coursepack (2021) addresses how to write an essay and serves as a Style Guide for writing the Response Papers (RPs) to be completed at the end of periods one to five. In addition, the study material provides a brief revision of some rules for good and consistent use of the language, in this case, American or British English.

Concretely, the first chapter addresses the basic steps in writing an essay (EUCLID 2021, 1-4). The second chapter covers the critical topic of plagiarism, why we must avoid that, and how (EUCLID 2021, 5-13). The third chapter suggests some rules to follow when writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16). Chapters 4 and 6 focus on the working language of the institution, which is English. Chapter 4 emphasizes the proper use of English (EUCLID 2021, 17-23), whereas chapter 6 compares standard American English and standard British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35). Chapters 5 and 8 address the topic of Rule of Style from different perspectives. While chapter 5 reflects on why a Style Guide is necessary (EUCLID 2021, 24-26), chapter 8 includes a summary of the Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-55), the Rule of Style recommended by EUCLID. Chapter 7 contains two examples of sample corrections to papers (EUCLID 2021, 36-43). And the

Deleted: P

last chapter, chapter 9, provides some tables, including standard Latin abbreviations and expressions used in writing (EUCLID 2021, 56–61).

The coursework also includes two videos facilitated by Prof. [Cleenerwerck](#), addressing how to use Zotero. In the first video, he explains how to install the program, save sources in the collection, and add references in our word document. The second video provides indications to retrieve metadata in the case of the Zotero entries, which are not automatically correctly formatted. Additionally, there is a third video in which Prof. [Cleenerwerck](#) guides us on using the word template for RPs facilitated by EUCLID. It also provides some recommendations regarding how to write a RP and indications on entering citations and references in the word document. Finally, it addresses as well what is the difference between these two concepts, [Rules of Style](#) and [Paragraph Style](#).

2) WRITING AN ESSAY: WHERE SHOULD WE START?

While the first chapter of the course pack presents the basics of essay writing, chapter [three](#) gives some rules of the [thumb](#) for writing papers. But, what is an essay? And a paper? Two definitions of essay included in the Oxford Advanced American Dictionary are: An essay (on something) is “a short piece of writing by a student as part of a course of study” or “a short piece of writing on a particular subject, written to be published.” A synonym for *essay* in the context of academic writing is *paper*. In any case, “an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.” (EUCLID 2021, 1).

During my academic career, I had to write several academic papers and essays. Therefore it has been beneficial to read the first and third chapters of the coursepack to check my approach when writing essays. Briefly, the basic steps in writing an essay are: determining the central thesis, pursuing exhaustive research of the topic, structuring and organizing your ideas, developing the first draft, and finally working on that first draft, editing and rewriting it, until you obtain the final version (EUCLID 2021, 1, 14).

I liked to see that I strictly follow some of the given recommendations, even though I was not completely conscious about it. For example, I try not to procrastinate and start working early to have enough time to read, and especially to think, to write the essay (EUCLID 2021, 1). During the research, I also tend not to take notes in the first reading to get an overview of the topic (EUCLID 2021, 2). To state a thesis is necessary to analyze the question, making sure that you understand that correctly and identify the key points (EUCLID 2021, 1). Otherwise, it will be complicated to know what you are required to do. For that reason, it is important to start making notes during your reading only when you have clarity of the question to be answered (EUCLID 2021, 3).

Once I start accumulating some ideas in my mind, I find it very helpful to include the main points that I want to discuss later in a first draft scheme. That helps me a lot to organize my ideas. And as stated in point number 4 of chapter one: “once you have a draft, you can work on writing well.” (EUCLID 2021, 3). One strategy that I use to cut down anxiety and overcome the white paper syndrome is to divide the writing task into several pieces and study sessions. I never try to write an essay entirely in just one session. It helps

Commented [GK1]: Note that the mere mention of a concept does not call for a citation. Limit citations to when information or facts are quoted!
Also, note that in the running text, numbers from 1-10 are written in words while 11 and above are written in figures.

Deleted: Cleenerwerck

Deleted: Cleenerwerck

Commented [GK2]: Avoid unnecessary capitalization!

Deleted: 3

Deleted: T

Deleted:

Commented [GK3]: Note that periods are only placed AFTER citations and not before them. Your punctuation could have been correct if a citation is not involved!

Commented [GK4]: Delete this period!

a lot as well start the text with the concepts and ideas in which you have more clarity, and then work step by step developing the other points (EUCLID 2021, 3). As suggested in the first chapter, I often write the conclusion and the introduction after the body.

Equally important to understanding the question is to avoid losing track of your thesis (EUCLID 2021, 1, 14). Therefore it is necessary to revise your drafts several times during the writing process and at the end. I find it helpful to read it out loud (EUCLID 2021, 16). In this revision process, I always let the draft aside for a few days to come back to that later with a fresh mind (EUCLID 2021, 1).

Finally, one critical point that I try to apply in other contexts, not only when writing an essay, is to evaluate and include different and sometimes opposing views (EUCLID 2021, 2). That allows you to get more contrasted and complete information on the topic. Moreover, it is a very enriching experience in all senses.

From all the given suggestions for writing papers, what surprised me the most were the following: “stay away from passive constructions” (EUCLID 2021, 15) and “use the first person” (EUCLID 2021, 16; Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3). I was often told to avoid the first person to increase the objectivity of my writing. However, sticking strictly to this rule could lead to the error of writing the own points of view, interpretations, and conclusions as objective announcements. I think that in specific contexts, the correct thing to do is to use the first person. Thus I was pleased to be encouraged to use it in my RPs.

3) PLAGIARISM

What is Plagiarism? In our study material for period 1, we can read that “plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source” (EUCLID 2021, 5). It seems to be a pretty straightforward concept. Nevertheless, this unethical practice would often be tolerated, and its incidence in the universities is high. The three-year (2002-2005) survey-study conducted by Donald McCabe on 83 different campuses in the US and Canada shows that 25% of 9,250 graduate students have engaged in 'cut and paste' Plagiarism at least once in the past year (McCabe 2005, 5). Another study conducted at the University of Lleida, Spain, reveals that 39.20 % of 2,098 students agreed with the statement that: “Copying and pasting from a website with no author is not plagiarism.” (Olivia-Dumitrina, Casanovas, and Capdevila 2019, 117) A qualitative research approach that investigated the incidents of plagiarism practices in two Universities in Tanzania concluded that 173 out of 453 students' papers were suspicious of Plagiarism (Anney and Mosha 2015, 211).

It seems that the high incidence of plagiarism and other similar unethical practices is a growing concern in higher education institutions. I, myself, found entire identical paragraphs in several reviews from different authors and institutions when, in 2016, I was writing the introduction of my master thesis about the development of the brain. One could argue that the information included in the reviews is common knowledge in the field. Moreover, in this case, previous publications from other authors that serve as sources of

Commented [GK5]: Delete this period and place another one after the citation!

Deleted: P

information were cited. However, from my point of view, there was a lack of acceptable use of paraphrasing.

Seeing the enormous extension of plagiarism and other similar unethical practices in higher education, the next question would be for me, why is it happening? Several studies approached this question (Olivia-Dumitrina, Casanovas, and Capdevila 2019; Carlin 2019; Drye, Lomo-David, and Snyder 2018; Anney and Mosha 2015). In these studies, they try to uncover the level of the students' understanding of academic integrity and their perception of the reasons that could explain the occurrence of academic dishonesty. Some authors argue that one influential factor had been incorporating new technologies into literacy processes, which so far has not been accompanied with good programs to train the students to use the digital tools respecting academic integrity (Olivia-Dumitrina, Casanovas, and Capdevila 2019; Anney and Mosha 2015).

Deleted: P

Among all the studies that I read, one that I found especially interesting is the approach of Matthew Carlin. Carlin analyses "the current state of ethics in higher education through an engagement with the concept of gnosticism - a term that refers most notably today to the modern compulsion to 'fix' an inherently fractured and malformed world." (2019, 436). In his article, Carlin concludes that:

Commented [GK6]: Delete this period!

Contemporary gnosticism in the form of progressive ideology has become ubiquitous in institutions of higher education today. Progressivism has weakened (not eliminated) ethics by rejecting the possibility of its universal or trans-historical relevance for the academy, . . . it has reassigned the act of moral discernment to the spheres of vitality, happiness, or politics. [Progressivism] . . . has replaced a focus on the transcendental as a framework for just and moral acts, with a focus on feelings, becomings, and individualized fulfillment. In contemporary higher education, ethics are conceived of as mere tools for one's own development. Cheating and Plagiarism, fraudulent research, and administrative corruption become easily justified as a means to attain personal advancement and success. Academic integrity and the pursuit of the truth becomes both irrelevant and impossible. The institutional sphere becomes a home for the unfolding of personal politics instead of an educational site oriented toward the promotion of what is universally good or true. (2019, 446)

In the last paragraph of the conclusions, Carlin proposes to the universities to reorient, distancing themselves from the dominance of progressivism. That would imply the disconnection from politics and individualism. He encourages the educational institutions to develop a new ethics "directed toward the fidelity of being" to align themselves "with a trans-historical, universal conception of the good." (2019, 447)

Commented [GK7]: Relocate the period to after the bracket. Always ensure there is a single space before a bracket!

4) WHY DO WE NEED A STYLE GUIDE?

To be able to answer this question, we should know what a style guide is. According to the study material included in the coursepack period one, a style guide is a conjunction of directives to ensure that all the text production associated with an institution, organization, or company are consistent and coherent in the writing style (EUCLID 2021, 24). These guidelines do not only include correct use of grammar, punctuation, and

vocabulary. In this case, the rules are well established, and consequently, it does not give so much space for debate. However, a style guide also includes many other aspects such as spelling, level of formality, sentence length, abbreviations, symbology, format features of the document, structure, etc. (EUCLID 2021, 24–25). Because there is a lack of a single authority regarding all these other aspects, a style guide is essential to standardize the writing style of a specific branch of knowledge or industry. This becomes especially relevant when there is a large number of contributing authors. Moreover, in certain contexts, a style guide includes branding considerations that search to create an identity or personality of the institution or business.

EUCLID recommends the Chicago style, specifically Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. This is also known as Turabian Style, and it consists of applying the Chicago style to research papers (EUCLID 2021, 44). It was constructive to consult the website of the Chicago Manual of Style (University of Chicago 2017), and I am sure I will go back to that whenever I have specific questions regarding the style.

Deleted: s

Deleted: s

Searching for other examples of style guides, I check the BBC News style guide entirely out of curiosity. Some of the entries included made me think how much influence it has the concrete selection of words that we use to describe or explain something. The combination of terms used, by itself, could determine our position regarding specific topics. For example, in the entry for abortion in the BBC News style guide, you can read:

Avoid pro-abortion, and use pro-choice instead. Campaigners favour a woman's right to choose, rather than abortion itself. And use anti-abortion rather than pro-life, except where it is part of the title of a group's name. (BBC n.d.)

We could find another example in the entry for sexual offenses:

The terms **child pornography** or **child porn** trivialise the nature of what is criminal material. We should use other language such as "**images that show child sex abuse**" or "**indecent images of children**". In headlines and/or summaries, use **child abuse images**. (BBC n.d.)

It seems clear that by the act of writing itself, and primarily when it is meant to be published, we carry a significant degree of responsibility with it.

5) THE DOMINANCE OF ENGLISH

Chapter six includes some fundamental differences between American and British English and influences of change. In the chapter's introduction, there are listed the main reasons why American English is dominant versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 27). When I was reading the opening, I reflected upon the extensive dominance of the English language overall. In this section, I build an overview of the topic by putting some numbers behind the facts.

Deleted: 6

It is clear that the total worth of the US economy explains the current dominance of American English extensively and consequently the dominance of English in general. But what is the actual number of people that speak English in the world? Is it the most spoken language? According to *Ethnologue*, the language with most native speakers is Chinese Mandarin, followed by Spanish (Eberhard, Simons, and Fennig 2021). In this case, English occupies the third position, with less than half of the native Chinese Mandarin speakers. However, if we include both native and non-native speakers, English becomes the most spoken language. Another interesting factor to mention is the distribution of both languages' uses. While Chinese Mandarin is concentrated mainly in Asia, English appears to spread out, having some presence on almost every continent. The greater number of non-native speakers and its spread out distribution is mainly due to historical reasons (i.e., colonialism). Finally, it is also important to notice that English has more than twice as many non-native speakers as native speakers. Therefore, in a more profound treatment of the subject would be very interesting to analyze, which is the influence of change that this factor has on the language. I liked to see that EUCLID references the diversity included in the English language by mentioning certain Ethnolects such as the "Black English" or Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish Influence (EUCLID 2021, 32–33). However, it would be insightful to include an overview of English's geography and its many varieties.

Finally, I would like to argue about one factor contributing enormously to the perpetuation of the dominance of English, in this case, American English: the massive extension of its use on the internet. I experienced that already during my Bachelor's. Whenever you searched for information on the internet to write your assignments or complement the given study material, you would generally find significantly more sources if you searched in English. That was the case also regarding minor clarifications or definitions of specific terms. Consequently, although the working language of the program was Catalan, English was extensively present. In fact, the usage of English on the internet in 2020 was 25.9 % of the world's participation (Internet World Stats 2021). This fact is not surprising if we consider that overall, the content in English published on the internet during 2021 exceeds 60% (W3Techs and Q-Success 2021).

6) STRUCTURE OF THE MATERIAL

When I was reviewing the course material, I quickly realized, as it is noticed on page II (EUCLID 2021, II), that the coursepack consists of a combination of different documents. Every document becomes a chapter of the final version of the study material. Although there is no problem with using several sources to build the chapters, I was missing a bit of order from my point of view.

For me would make more sense to structure the material as follows. In the first part of the document, I would include chapters [one](#) and [three](#), as both chapters give some recommendations and suggestions on how to write a paper. Then I would add, as follows, the chapter regarding Plagiarism. In the third part of the document, I would add all the chapters focusing on style rules. I would start with chapter [five](#), give an overview of the topic, and continue with chapter 8 to provide a summary of the recommended concrete Style guide. A fourth part will cover all the issues regarding the English language. Here I

Deleted: 1

Deleted: 3

Deleted: 5

would include chapters [four](#) and [six](#). Following I would put chapter [nine](#). Finally, at the end of the document, as an additional chapter, or even as an appendix, I would position chapter [seven](#).

Deleted: 4

Deleted: 6

Deleted: 9

Deleted: 7

That is only a suggestion, which results from how I structured the information while studying and working on the material.

7) CONCLUSION

This first period of the ACA-401 course represents my beginning to the master's degree in [international public health](#) at EUCLID. When I started this response paper, I reflected on the importance that EUCLID gives to this first course, considering that it is a general course that every new student of all the offered programs should go through.

Deleted: I

Deleted: P

Deleted: H

After studying the material and getting a bit more familiar with EUCLID's methods, I could completely understand the relevance of this first course. EUCLID is an intergovernmental institution, which offers mainly online distance programs for affordable prices. Considering all these specific characteristics, it is expected the profile of the students to be very diverse. Within this framework, the need for standardization takes significance. Apart from instructing the new students in writing specifically a response paper, EUCLID is also standardizing the level of its students concerning writing papers in general, ensuring that all the students acquire the minimum required writing skills to proceed with their program.

These are some of the concluding points of great importance covered in this first period. While academic essay writing should be based on evidence, one should not underestimate the utility of the first person singular. Conscious of the growing concern that Plagiarism represents nowadays in higher education, EUCLID states clearly from the very first day its position towards this "serious academic offense." Another question regarding Plagiarism and similar practices is if the broader academic community is ready to build an ethical framework to promote universal good. Moreover, with this study material, EUCLID makes sure that everyone understands the rules of style and why they are critical. Second, it ensures that everyone has access to the indispensable tools in this regard. It provides all the sources necessary to get detailed information about the institution's generally recommended guide style, [Turabian's](#) style. Finally, it emphasizes the correct use of the working language, whether it is American English or British English. Because being the dominant language does not prevent you from grammar, spelling, punctuation, and mechanic mistakes of your many users.

Deleted: Tarubian's

There is no doubt that the ACA-401 period [one](#) is a powerful approach to the new students. Ultimately, it provided me with the essential background to proceed with my study at EUCLID. Besides, as Duncan Green says: "Floundering around, learning by doing but also by failing, is not only good but inevitable." Learning by doing is a very effective practice, plus it gives the chance to learn from your own mistakes. Thus, the best way to learn how to write a RP applying all the points covered in this period is by doing it and paying attention to your instructor's valuable feedback.

Deleted: 1

REFERENCES

Anney, Vicent Naano, and Mary Atanas Mosh. "Student's Plagiarisms in Higher Learning Institutions in the Era of Improved Internet Access: Case Study of Developing Countries." *Journal of Education and Practice* 6, no. 13 (2015): 203–16.

Formatted: Justified

BBC. "BBC News Style Guide." Accessed November 4, 2021. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/newsstyleguide/>.

Carlin, Matthew. "Gnosticism, Progressivism and the (Im)Possibility of the Ethical Academy." *Educational Philosophy and Theory* 53, no. 5 (October 2019): 436–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2019.1683825>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper (RP)*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Deleted: "

Deleted: "

Formatted: Font: Italic

Deleted: (Januar 2021): 1–12.

Drye, Sherrie L., Ewuukgem Lomo-David, and Lisa Gueldenzoph Snyder. "Normal Deviance: An Analysis of University Policies and Student Perceptions of Academic Dishonesty." *Southern Journal of Business and Ethics* 10 (2018): 71–84.

Eberhard, David M., Gary F. Simons, and Charles D. Fennig. "What Is the Most Spoken Language?" *Ethnologue: Languages of the World*. Accessed November 3, 2021. <http://www.ethnologue.com>.

Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period I*, 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University.

Deleted: "

Formatted: Font: Italic

Deleted: "

Deleted: (2021): 1–61.

Internet World Stats. "Top Ten Internet Languages in the World - Internet Statistics." Accessed November 3, 2021. <https://www.internetworldstats.com/stats7.htm>.

McCabe, Donald L. "Cheating among College and University Students: A North American Perspective." *International Journal for Educational Integrity* 1, no. 1 (November 2005): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.21913/IJEI.v1i1.14>.

Olivia-Dumitrina, Nechita, Montserrat Casanovas, and Yolanda Capdevila. "Academic Writing and the Internet: Cyber-Plagiarism amongst University Students." *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research* 8, no. 2 (July 2019): 112–125. <https://doi.org/10.7821/naer.2019.7.407>.

University of Chicago. "The Chicago Manual of Style, 17th Edition (2017)." *The Chicago Manual of Style Online*. Accessed October 26, 2021. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org>.

W3Techs, Q-success. "Historical Trends in the Usage Statistics of Content Languages for Websites, November 2021." Accessed November 4, 2021. https://w3techs.com/technologies/history_overview/content_language.

Formatted: Justified, Indent: Left: 0 cm, Hanging: 1.27 cm

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.